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The relationship between Religions **and Accounting Standards**

This research was done by Nidhal Al-Shanti, Masters degree student in accounting, accountability and governance.

Abstract:

Religions are giving many responsibilities to their followers to make them accountable. Being accountable is the nature of the human being and people are accountable for different reasons, due to the religion, due to the law, due to their company's policy, or due even to their personalities. In this research we will try to study the common areas between Islam and Christianity in how they make their followers accountable and at the same time we will study the impact of the religions on the accounting standards...

Contents

Introduction	3
Religions overview	5
Common areas between Christianity and Islam	6
<i>Tithe or Zakah</i>	6
<i>Inheritance or Mirath</i>	7
<i>Usury or Riba</i>	9
<i>How Christianity and Islam make their followers accountable?</i>	9
International Accounting Standards	11
Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (“AAOIFI”)	13
Critical thinking	16
<i>Why international accounting standards?</i>	16
<i>Why the adoption of IFRS if they have AAOIFI?</i>	17
Conclusion	18
Bibliography	21

Introduction

Within a minute from the time you started to read this research, an average of 250 babies are born! Which means an increase in the population by 131.4 million people in the next 365 days. This number is not a small number at all! Everyday our world is becoming bigger and our economy is becoming more globalized along with the development of technology.

Since globalization is defined as the interaction between companies, governments and people; the benefits would be mixing the culture of people, increase profits for companies and make the trade between governments easier. This seems really nice! But let us think deeply about this term and imagine how the world will look like, since the globalization makes people, companies and governments work abroad or in a wider range, this will increase the financial transactions every moment and if we think deeper about how it works, we may feel like we live in a “whirlpool” where everything moves very fast in an unorganized way! This is really risky and dangerous as this may increase the number of scandals and from the “internet bubble” period we have learned a free lesson how globalization and technology can affect our life, when the scandal of Enron happened which is classified by the economists as one of the biggest scandals ever happened! So, what is the solution? what can we do in this case? how can we control and reduce these scandals? Should every company be aligned with a “watch dog” to control its activity? Or we should stop improving the technology? No, the action required is much easier than what we imagine, it is basically to make the people accountable and responsible for their actions!

From the beginning of humanity, the human being is responsible in a way or another. If we take the “stone age” era as an example, people were responsible for their actions, if a person had woken up in the morning feeling lazy, this person would have slept hungry at night! Since the creation, carrying the responsibilities is part of our nature as human being, at least each person of us is carrying his/her responsibility, but some people also take the responsibility of others, we can take an example two persons who are classified as two of the most influential people of all time according to Wealthy Gloria¹, Jesus Christ and Prophet Muhammed; they basically took the responsibility of inviting people to what they

¹ (Wealthyorilla, n.d.)

believe in and giving their followers their responsibilities and make them accountable to their actions according to Canon law and Sharia'a law.

Religions did not come to make differences between people as we all at the end are human being, basically; we believe that religions are simpler than that, we believe that religions are a way of living. These two religions and all the other religions encourage their followers to do good things, the religion instills the art of stewardship into their members, they all make their followers responsible to others! They all give a proper guidance on how to deal with others! However, if we keep going through the history, we will see easily that within the time more responsibilities came up either by law or by sciences. For example; Laws and Rules were created to stop people from doing crimes and make them responsible for their actions. The accounting standards as well; they were created to make the accountants responsible to manage, control and keep records of the owners' or investors' money!

So, what is accountability? And what is the link between religions and accountability? What is the link between accountability and accounting?

We are doing this research to study the history of accountability and accounting and answer the following research questions:

- a) What are the common areas between Christianity and Islam related to the financial transactions which make the people accountable?
- b) What are the effects of religions on the current accounting and accountability standards?

As a starting point and to be able to answer these questions, we need to understand what accountability means? According to Rick Stapenhurst in his paper "Accountability in Governance" which was published by the World bank, "The notion of accountability is an amorphous concept that is difficult to define in precise terms. However, broadly speaking, accountability exists when there is a relationship where an individual or body, and the performance of tasks or functions by that individual or body, are subject to another's oversight, direction or request that they provide information or justification for their actions."

Religions overview

As we mentioned in our introduction, we believe that religions are way of living as all the religions encourage their followers to do good deeds and help others. Some religions also mentioned accounting and accountability in different occasions, but we decided to study Christianity and Islam as they are the major two religions in the world. Since we are talking about religions and accounting, it would be really nice to present and mention some facts about accounting in these two religions, for example²:

- 1) “Accounting/accounts” as words were mentioned in Quran 48 times,
- 2) In some parts of Quran, some calculations were mentioned as well in relation to inheritance
- 3) Financial statements are old methodology to control the money! Which will be explained later in the following sections

Another interesting fact is that “Accountable” as a word, mentioned eight times in the Bible³. Both religions make their followers accountable to others in many different areas. For example, Bible; in many different occasions; speaks about responsibilities or in another words “being accountable” to the actions we do; some of these occasions as follows:

- a) “for each one should carry their own load”⁴
- b) “If a man seduces a virgin who is not pledged to be married and sleeps with her, he must pay the bride-price, and she shall be his wife”⁵
- c) “...You shall assign to them as their responsibility all they are to carry”⁶

However, since we are studying the impact of religions on accounting standards, we decided to study three topics in common between Christianity and Islam on how to make people accountable. These topics are:

- a) Tithe (“Zakah” in Islam),
- b) Inheritance (“Mirath” in Islam), and
- c) Usury (“Riba” in Islam).

² (Al-Buhaisi, 1996)

³ (Ezekiel 3:18; Ezekiel 3:20; Ezekiel 33:6; Ezekiel 33:8; Ezekiel 34:10; Daniel 6:2; Jonah 1:14 and Romans 3:19)

⁴ (Galatians 6:5)

⁵ (Exodus 22:16)

⁶ (Numbers 4:27)

Common areas between Christianity and Islam

1) Tithe or Zakah

Both religions ask the followers to pay tithe. According to Christianity, tithe is different in the old testament and the new testament. The Lexicon of Evangelical Christianity defines tithe as “a tenth of one’s income offered to God” for the purpose of supporting church operations.⁷ According to Leviticus 27:30, “a tithe of everything from the land, whether grain from the soil or fruit from the trees, belong to the lord; it is holy to the lord”⁸, and according to Numbers 18:28 “... you must present a tenth of that tithe as the Lord’s offering”⁹; in addition to the article issued by Ervin Budiselić in 2014 “The Role and the Place of Tithing in the Context of Christian Giving Part 1”, the tithes is being given to a portion of the land or income has to be given to the church in order to use these portions for social programs but the followers have to give tithe before they cover the other needs, but the question; is there a specific portion to be given? According to “The Catechism of the Full Gospel Church” and the definition above, the tithe is a tenth of all the income.¹⁰

Tithe in Islam is called “Zakah” which is “a form of worship which involves wealth, when a Muslim person’s earnings reach a prescribed amount in excess of his needs, that person is required to pay a portion of his earnings to the poor and needy”.¹¹ Islam is clear when it comes to Zakah, it is mentioned in many places in Quran and Prophet Muhammed’s actions and guidance (“Sunnah”) that Muslims should do it, below are evidences from Quran:

- a) “And establish prayer and give zakah and bow with those who bow”¹²
- b) “...And speak to people good [words] and establish prayer and give zakah”¹³
- c) “Restrain your hands [from fighting] and establish prayer and give zakah”¹⁴

⁷ (Budiselić, 2014)

⁸ (Leviticus 27:30)

⁹ (Numbers 18:28)

¹⁰ (Budiselić, 2014)

¹¹ (Hossain, 2012)

¹² (Surat Al-Baqarah verse 43)

¹³ (Surat Al-Baqarah verse 83)

¹⁴ (Surat Al-Nesa verse 77)

However, Quran and Sunnah oblige Muslims to do Zakah based on the following conditions¹⁵:

- a) the person should be Muslim,
- b) the person should be Adult, and
- c) the person should reach a certain amount of extra wealth

Islam has provided a proper guidance on how to do Zakah, when to do it, to who it must be. Zakah according to Islam is 2.5% on money which the people own according to what the Prophet Muhammed used to do. According to the Islamic history, the prophet Muhammed used to ask people to pay 5 coins against every 200 coins which means 2.5% of money but Zakah is not only on money, it also should be paid on other properties such as gold, commodities and wheat.¹⁶

2) Inheritance or Mirath

Inheritance in general means transferring the ownership of an asset from a person (person A) to another person (person B) after the death of the first person (person A). This happens in most of the cases between parent and children. In some cases, inheritance can be gotten prior to the death of the parent, it could be given when and if requested by the benefactor. Almost all major religions spoke about inheritance and give a guidance on it, but when it comes to Christianity, inheritance is not only on assets, but it is also on the gifts which God plans to give to people. Inheritance in Bible is very important and as a word, it was mentioned more than 30 times. Below are some of the verses where inheritance was mentioned in Bible:

- a) “A good man leaves an inheritance to his children’s children, and the wealth of the sinner is stored up for the righteous”¹⁷
- b) “house and wealth are an inheritance from fathers, but a prudent wife is from the lord”¹⁸
- c) “the younger of them said to his father ‘Father, give me the share of the estate that falls to me’ so he divided his wealth between them”¹⁹

¹⁵ (Dhar, 2013)

¹⁶ (Dhar, 2013)

¹⁷ (Proverbs 13:22)

¹⁸ (Proverbs 19:14)

¹⁹ (Luke 15:12)

Concerning the topic inheritance, the question is how is it being done in Christianity? And are there specific people to be given the assets?

According to the holly Bible, the only difference between shares is the share of the first son who has to get double share (birth right) than the others²⁰, because the first son according to birth right is considered the heir. In Christianity, not only sons are considered as heirs, daughters as well as brothers (uncles) can also be heirs if the father has no sons as mentioned in the Bible²¹. According to the Bible; if a man dies with no sons, the inheritance goes to the daughters, if no daughters; to his brothers, if no brothers; to his father's brothers; if no father's brothers; then to the nearest relative in his clan²².

In addition, Islam also speaks about inheritance. There are three evidences from Quran giving a detailed guidance on how to divide the wealth of a person after his/her death. They are as follows:

- a) "From what is left by parents and those nearest related there is a share for men and a share for women whether the property be small or large..."²³
- b) "to the male, a portion equal to that of two females: if only daughters, two or more, their share is two-thirds of the inheritance; if only one, her share is a half. For parents, a sixth share of the inheritance to each, if the deceased left children; if no children, and the parents are the (only) heirs, the mother has a third; if the deceased Left brothers (or sisters) the mother has a sixth. (The distribution in all cases ('s) after the payment of legacies and debts. Ye know not whether your parents or your children are nearest to you in benefit. These are settled portions ordained by Allah; and Allah is All-knowing, Al-wise."²⁴
- c) "(12) In what your wives leave, your share is a half, if they leave no child; but if they leave a child, ye get a fourth; after payment of legacies and debts. In what ye leave, their share is a fourth, if ye leave no child; but if ye leave a child, they get an eighth; after payment of legacies and debts. If the man or woman whose inheritance is in question, has left neither ascendants nor descendants, but has left a brother or a sister, each one of the two gets a sixth; but if more than two, they share in a third; after payment of legacies and debts; so that

²⁰ (Deuteronomy 21:15-17)

²¹ (Deuteronomy 21:15-17)

²² (Numbers 27:8-11)

²³ (Surat Al-Nesa verse 7)

²⁴ (Surat Al-Nesa verse 11)

no loss is caused (to any one). Thus is it ordained by Allah; and Allah is All-knowing, Most Forbearing (**13**) Those are limits set by Allah: those who obey Allah and His Messenger will be admitted to Gardens with rivers flowing beneath, to abide therein (forever) and that will be the supreme achievement (**14**) But those who disobey Allah and His Messenger and transgress His limits will be admitted to a Fire, to abide therein: And they shall have a humiliating punishment.”²⁵

3) Usury or Riba

Generally, usury or interest is the difference between the repayment loan amount and the original loan amount. In other words, a specific portion or percentage being paid on the original amount and has to be paid along with the loan itself. However; both religions prohibited usury or interest. If we talk about Christianity, the Bible speaks in different occasions about the prohibition of usury such as:

- a) “If you lend money to any of my people with you who is poor, you shall not be like a moneylender to him, and you shall not exact interest from him”²⁶
- b) “...Take no interest from him or profit...you shall not lend him your money at interest...”²⁷
- c) “You shall not charge interest on loans to your brother...”²⁸

Usury (“Riba”) in Islam is the late return penalty levied on the loan returned after the due date. Riba and Interest in Islam have the same concept. Quran has forbidden Riba and Interest in many different occasions such as:

- a) “...but Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury...”²⁹
- b) “...Allah will deprive usury of all blessing...”³⁰
- c) “O ye who believe! Devour not usury...”³¹

How Christianity and Islam make their followers accountable?

Both religions have some specific rules, require and in some cases oblige their followers to follow them. In the above section, we explained three of the common areas between both

²⁵ (Surat Al-Nesa verse 12,13 and 14)

²⁶ (Exodus verse 22:25)

²⁷ (Leviticus verses 25:35-37)

²⁸ (Deuteronomy verse 23:19)

²⁹ (Surat Al-Baqarah verse 275)

³⁰ (Surat Al-Baqarah verse 276)

³¹ (Surat Al-Imran verse 139)

religions, but the question is, how the religions make their followers accountable? generally speaking, if we think deeply about the above areas, we can notice easily that people should support each other and should be accountable to each other. Tithe or Zakah for example are supposed to be given directly to either to the poor people and people who are in need or the amount also can be given to a specialized institution to give it to the deserved people. Also, when we talk about the inheritance, Quran and Bible have provided guidance to their followers to guarantee that the brothers can't take the shares of their sisters, or the wife should give her children their shares, or even the grand parents can't take the shares of their grandchildren.

While when it comes to usury, we can see that the lender is taking the advantage of the borrower as the borrower is in a need of money for a reason or another, and basically; according to both religions; rich people should fulfill the needs of the poor people for the sake of God's pleasure³², by doing so; the followers are accountable to help each other.

Merely 3% of the papers published on accounting journals were about religion in the period between 2000 and 2008 according to the study made by Maramoros and Hidalgo in 2010. This fact shows that few studies were made to understand the relation between religions and accounting. Carmona and Ezzamel in 2016 noted that the relationship between religion, religious institutions and accounting is scanty. In 2004, Gorringer and Gray noticed that the accounting academics do not take religion and theology into their consideration.³³

Usury, inheritance and tithe are some transactions or deals people face every day! So, the question now what is the position of the standards on these topics? And to what extent the religions affected the standards? These questions are really wide and since our focus in the paper is usury, tithe and inheritance, we will focus on these areas and compare the position of religions on these three areas and the position of IFRS and AAOIFI on the same areas, but to answer these questions, studying religions only is not enough, we should also study the accounting standards in Christian countries and Muslim countries to understand their history as well.

³² (Ahmad & Syed, 2018)

³³ (Cordery, 2015)

International Accounting Standards

Accounting as science is an old science which was implemented approximately 3,500 B.C. but it was in a different way. No double entry was there; it was just a way of keeping the commercial records.³⁴ Accounting history is too long and rich with information and details which we may need to understand how important the standards are and how the standards were implemented and keep being implemented. According to V. Tkach and M. Tkach, accounting history can be divided into the following stages³⁵:

- a) Trade stage until 1800,
- b) Entrepreneurial stage from 1800 to 1900,
- c) Organizational stage from 1900 to 1950,
- d) Optimization stage from 1950 to 1975, and
- e) Strategic stage since 1975.

For us, since we are studying the history of accounting standards and the effects of religions on the standards; we are just going to cover in this research the “organizational stage”, “Optimization stage” and “Strategic stage” as these stages are the ones when the accounting standards were created and for the other stages, please refer to “History of origins and development of system international accounting” which was published by Melnyk Nataliya in 2013. We have also to highlight the fact that we are studying the development of international accounting standards but not the development of accounting standards in specific countries.

The end of 19th century and beginning of 20th century is full of significant events which led to the accounting frameworks and standards we are having now. Several countries have created and passed laws and accounting frameworks in order to establish an international system of accounting. In 1904, the first meeting took place in the United states to discuss the main issues of accounting and economy; the accountants who attended the meeting came from different countries such as U.S., England, Netherlands, Canada and Scotland. Here we have to highlight that Scotland is one of the first countries who created an accounting framework in the world. 15 countries represented by 370 attendees where there in the

³⁴ (Alexander, 2002)

³⁵ (Nataliya, 2013)

meeting which took place in 1926, during this meeting; the attendees shared their knowledge and experience in order to find a universal treatment for costing accounting. Following to the great depression which happened in 1929, the developed countries noticed some huge deficiencies in the accounting systems in the that period, the differences were not only across countries, but they were even across the companies in the same country. Therefore; the idea of creating an international legal framework to create international accounting standards grew more and the countries started to work on it very hard. By the end of 1950s and due to the increase in global economic following to the end of the 2nd world war, the “spotlight” was routed to the problem of international accounting and auditing standards.

The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (“AICPA”) finally created its own committee in 1962 with the aim of creating a program between accountants in different countries to exchange ideas and experience. AISG (“Accountants International Study Group”) was created in 1966 to study the accounting standards in England, Wales, United States and Canada with the aim of attempting to harmonize the accounting and auditing practices in these countries in the long run. In 1972, an important proposal was on the table when the AISG representatives met to discuss the creation of International Accounting Standards Committee (“IASC”) and the committee was formed in 1973 consisted of eleven (11) countries from different continentals, and a year later; six (6) more countries joined the association. Officially, the IASC issued the first standards about transparency of accounting policy in 1975 and till 2003, 41 standards were issued by the IASC under the name of International Accounting Standards (“IASs”) before it changed its name from “IASC” to “International Accounting Standards Board” (“IASB”) and before the issuance of the “International Financial Accounting Standards” (“IFRS”) became into the stage to replace or to update the IASs. When the IASC started to issue the standards in 1975, the countries were encouraged to do more in relation to this topic especially after they noticed the improvement in economy and the improvements in relations between the countries, so; in 1977; from Munich, another good news came to the globe when the International Federation of Accountants was founded with the aim of strengthening the accounting profession in the interest of the society. In the early of 21st century, the concept of “standards harmonization” or in other words, “international convergence” became more “international” and many countries are working hard on it in order to have an international accounting standard.³⁶

³⁶ (Nataliya, 2013)

Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions

(“AAOIFI”)

U.S. GAAP and IFRS are the most commonly used accounting standards in the world especially when the companies start to invest in foreign countries. After the first world war and along with the great depression happened in that period, there was a need of making international accounting standards in order to protect the economy from another depression and that's why many conferences and meetings were taking place to reach this goal, but when we talk about Muslim countries, there are very few resources to rely on but due to the growth in Islamic financial institutions, the development of universities in Muslim countries³⁷ in addition to the restrictions in Islam on interests and usury as well as the obligation of Zakah and the fair inheritance, there was a need of implementing specific accounting standards for the Muslim countries. Since we are talking about Muslim countries, we are talking about more than 40 countries in the world with a majority Muslim population, out of this number, there are 22 Arab countries and one of them is a leading country and considered as a holly place or country for Muslims which is Saudi Arabia. The accounting standards in Arab Countries were implemented and adopted based on the International Financial Accounting Standards (“IFRS”),³⁸ but some of the accounting standards in some Muslim countries were implemented based on Sharia'a law which is referred to Quran and Sunnah. The standards are being used in Muslim countries are called “Sharia'a Standards” which are being issued by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (“AAOIFI”)³⁹.

AAOIFI is an Islamic International not-for-profit body that prepares accounting, auditing, governance, ethics and Sharia'a standards for Islamic financial institutions and the industry. It was established in 1991 and based in Bahrain. These standards are adopted as mandatory requirements in forty-five (45) Muslim countries.⁴⁰

³⁷ (Napier, 2007)

³⁸ (Accounting and financial studies series, 2018)

³⁹ (Full text of sharia'ah standards for Islamic financial institutions, 2017)

⁴⁰ (A study of financial statements of Islamic financial institutions, 2015)

As of November 2017, the AAOIFI has issued a total of ninety-eight (98) standards which are divided into the following categories:

- a) Fifty-eight (58) standards as Sharia'a standards,
- b) Twenty-six (26) standards as Accounting standards,
- c) Seven (7) standards as Governance standards,
- d) Five (5) standards as auditing standards, and
- e) Two (2) standards as Code of ethics

In March 2015, the Asian-Oceanian Standard-Setters Board made a study on the financial statements of Islamic institutions in 40 countries. The sample selected in this study was based on the classification of the top Islamic financial institutions by Countries which was published in November 2013 in *The Banker*. 132 financial institutions were selected to meet the objective of this study⁴¹. However, some countries were excluded from this study due either the ineligibility to get full set of financial statements or the ineligibility to get the financial statements in English. The sample selected in this study and the results country by country is presented in the next page, but before we represent the table; we highlight once again that the sample selected was only the Islamic institutions in the countries selected as a sample⁴².

⁴¹ (A study of financial statements of Islamic financial institutions, 2015)

⁴² (A study of financial statements of Islamic financial institutions, 2015)

Sample selected and results of the study in country wise⁴³:

<i>Country name</i>	<i>What standards adopted?</i>
Albania	IFRS
Australia	IFRS
Bahrain	AAOIFI and IFRS (optional)
Bangladesh	AAOIFI and Local standards (optional)
Bosnia	IFRS
Brunei	Local standards
Egypt	Local standards
India	Local standards
Indonesia	Local standards
Iran	Local standards
Jordan	AAOIFI
Kazakhstan	IFRS
Kuwait	IFRS
Lebanon	AAOIFI
Malaysia	IFRS
Mauritius	AAOIFI
Oman	AAOIFI
Pakistan	Local standards
Philippines	Local standards
Qatar	AAOIFI and IFRS (optional)
Saudi Arabia	IFRS
South Africa	IFRS
Siri Lanka	Local standards
Sudan	AAOIFI
Switzerland	Local standards
Thailand	Local standards
Turkey	Local standards and IFRS (optional)
United Arab Emirates	IFRS
United Kingdom	IFRS
United States	U.S. GAAP
Yemen	IFRS

From the table above, we can see that many Islamic institutions do not adopt AAOIFI, but they adopt either the local standards or the international ones.

⁴³ (A study of financial statements of Islamic financial institutions, 2015)

Critical thinking

After we introduced the position of religions on the common areas and the history of accounting standards (both, IFRS and AAOIFI), we should analyze and think critically about the relation between religion and the accounting standards and to what extent they affected each other which will be covered as part of the conclusion.

Although both religions prohibited usury, but within the time and along with the advancement of economy and technology, usury becomes as a business, if we look at the banks and the financial institutions for example, the main profits come from the interest charged on loans.

If we look at IFRS and study them, we can see that there are no standards related to inheritance and tithe and at the same time there are two standards talking about interest or usury (IAS 23 and IAS 39) but these two standards give guidance on how to record and account them, but on the other hand, if we look at AAOIFI, we can see that there are specific standards related to these topics, for example “SS 2” speaks about interest and usury, “SS 35” speaks about Zakah while inheritance is covered by four (4) different standards as it is a complicated and a very wide topic; these standards are “SS 26”, “SS 29”, “SS 42” and “SS 50”.

Why international accounting standards?

The question is, why do countries adopt international accounting standards even though these standards are not in compliance with religious views like usury? Or what is the benefit of having international accounting standards applied by all countries? Many researches were made in order to study the importance of applying international standards instead of local standards. Barth in 2008 studied the financial information of 21 countries and she found that the accounting practices quality increased after adopting the international standards comparing to the “pre-adoption” period while Meeks and Swann in 2009 analyzed the adoption of IFRS at a firm level and they found that the companies experienced higher accounting quality. Latridis in 2010 found that the financial performance affected positively based on the sample he studied based on the data collected from firms listed in London Stock Exchange markets. These are not the only results as Esptein in 2009 found that the international financial reporting standards increase market liquidity, reduce the transaction

cost and the cost of capital formation while Cai and Wong in 2010 noticed that international standards will increase the level of integration among the capital markets who are adopting international standards.⁴⁴

In addition, according to the “Use of IFRS Standards around the World” document, the IFRS foundation declared that “the mission of the foundation is to bring transparency, accountability and efficiency to the financial markets”. In the same document; they also declared that “IFRS Standards strengthen accountability by reducing the information gap between the providers of capital and the people to whom they have entrusted their money. The standards provide information needed to hold management to account. As a source of globally comparable information, IFRS Standards are also of vital importance to regulators around the world”.⁴⁵

Why the adoption of IFRS if they have AAOIFI?

But another question is why Muslim countries apply international standards if they have Sharia’a standards? as we mentioned above, AAOIFI standards are only applicable to the Islamic Financial Institutions and this type of business is not the only business in Muslim countries. However, the adoption of the international accounting standards in some Muslim countries refer to many different reasons, for example; the adoption of IFRS in Gulf countries is due to the fact that the economic development in gulf countries is so fast so they need to stay in the market in order to get and have new investments and open to the international market. The huge foreign population in Gulf countries also played a role in the adoption of the IFRS. While the reason of adopting the IFRS in the levant countries is to attract new investments as these countries’ economy is weak and they need to refresh it with new investments and due to the fact that these countries do not have local committees to set the local accounting standards⁴⁶, even Saudi Arabia updated their own Zakah standard named “Zakah accounting standard/1999” due to the globalization, this accounting standard was issued in 1999 and all the companies who operate in Saudi Arabia had to adopt it but in 2016, when the Saudi Arabia government decided to implement VAT in accordance with the other Gulf Countries, Saudi Organization for Certified Public Accountants (“SOCPA”),

⁴⁴ (Madawaki, 2012)

⁴⁵ (Use of IFRS standards around the world, 2018)

⁴⁶ (Accounting and financial studies series, 2018)

decided to update this standard by applying it only to the local companies, and applying it only to the Saudi's citizens who invest in foreign companies but they operate in Saudi Arabia.⁴⁷

Conclusion

Religions and accounting standards are important in a way or another. Religions are important to their followers in a different way based on their faith but the important thing here is that all religions make their followers accountable. Accounting standards are the same, they are created, made, updated and give guidance to the firms in order to make them accountable to their investors or even to the economy but when it comes to “what extent accounting standards are affected by the religions”, it is somehow different but why? If we look at the international standards (IFRS), we can see as we explained above that there are no specific standards prohibit the common topics were covered but instead, there are two standards related to usury or interest explain how they should be accounted. In their paper “Usury and Credit Practices in the Middle Ages” which was published in 2018, Adamo, Alexander and Fasiello; the Church was not able to inhibit the credit activities, and it favored the development of the credit activities, however; “The Church itself would not have been able to survive without credit (Gilchrist, 1969), and it used the usury prohibition to regulate loan markets, enhancing credit at low cost when the papacy was a borrower (Ekelund, Hébert, and Tollison, 1989: 328) or using the prohibition as a weapon to squash rival emerging powers and to maintain its wealth and authority (Fontaine, 2014: 68)”.⁴⁸

According to the above paragraph and although Christianity does not allow usury at least in the past, nowadays the Church allows it, this can be evidenced and proofed by the Canon law in the financial field which was issued for the first time in 1917 and later on updated in 1983. If we look at these two dates, we can say that the Canon law was issued after the idea of creating an international accounting framework was passed in 1904 and the update one (the current one) was issued in 1983 which means after the International Accounting Standards Committee (“IASC”) started to issue international standards in 1975. In addition, the Canon law required the Diocesan Finance Council which is the committee who helps

⁴⁷ (Zakah accounting standard, 2016)

⁴⁸ (Adamo, Alexander, & Fasiello, 2018)

the bishop in his responsibilities in the financial field, for example; according to Canon law no. 493, the Diocesan Finance Council has to "...prepare each year, according to the directions of the diocesan bishop, a budget of the income and expenditures which are foreseen for the entire governance of the diocese in the coming year, and at the end of the year examines an account of the revenues and expenses", this is somehow similar to the financial statements prepared by the firms. Another example is Canon law no. 2.5 where the Church says "pay at the stated time the interest due on a loan or mortgage and take care that the capital debt itself is repaid in a timely manner" which is an evidence also that the Church allows usury.

However, when it comes to the accounting standards in Muslim countries, AAOIFI has a different relationship with the religion. All AAOIFI standards were built based on the religion, therefore; we can say that the accounting standards in Muslim countries are highly affected by the religion.

The relationship between religion and accounting standards is not only "the extent of impact" on each other. There is another important relationship between them. They both make their followers accountable for their actions and behavior. Religions make their followers accountable to God and to people while accounting standards make their followers accountable to the investors, firms and economy. In addition, the religions support the idea of accounting standards, the "Islamic caliphate" in the past had created an organization or a committee named "Bayt Al-Mal" which means in English "The house of Money". Bayt Al-Mal was responsible for the following⁴⁹:

- 1) Control the revenues of people
- 2) Control the expenditures of people
- 3) Control the properties of people and their businesses
- 4) Make sure that investors issue documents to the consumers and receive documents from suppliers based on their agreements
- 5) Make sure that investors have their "logo" or "trade name" so the investors can be recognized from each other.

⁴⁹ (Al-Buhaisi, 1996)

In addition to the above responsibilities, Bayt Al-Mal was also responsible to report the financial transactions to the Wali (“the president”). There was “daily book” where the revenues recorded in a daily basis with mentioning the day, date and the name of the donator and then the expenditures were recorded based on the day, date and to who the money was given to. In addition to the “daily book”, there was another book named “store book” for recording the material donations like rice, sugar, oil, commodities in general, these items were recorded based on the day, date and the donator with no cost recorded, just the weight of these items. After preparing the daily book and the store book and in a periodical wise, financial statements were prepared and given to the “Wali or president” at that period based on the total revenues, total expenditures and then the remaining balance will be mentioned as “cash on hand” with mentioning also the items they have in the store. ⁵⁰

This is not the only example, but also the Church was accountable to its followers when it noticed that it is not able to inhibit the development of credit practices, so it differentiated between the concept of interest and usury by saying that interest is being calculated at moderate rate while usury was identified and connected only to loan operations and then it made the followers accountable as well when it obliged them to go and confess at least once a year.⁵¹ This is also an evidence that the religion is supporting the accounting standards.

Nowadays, as we mentioned in the introduction; our economy size is increasing and along with the globalization concept we may face more scandals and the only solution is to make people accountable, so; it does not matter who has an impact on the other, it does not matter what religion the person follows, it does not matter what standards the firm or the company follows, what matters basically is to be accountable to our actions. Religions and accounting standards, they both; make their followers accountable and this is the most important thing to face our economic problems.

⁵⁰ (Al-Buhaisi, 1996)

⁵¹ (Adamo, Alexander, & Fasiello, 2018)

Bibliography

(2015). *A study of financial statements of Islamic financial institutions*. Asian-Oceania standard-setters group.

(2018). *Accounting and financial studies series*. Arab Monetary Fund.

Adamo, S., Alexander, D., & Fasiello, R. (2018). Usury and credit practices in the middle ages.

Ahmad, K., & Syed, F. (2018). Muamma (conundrum) of Riba (interest and usury) in major religions in general and in Islam in particular.

Al-Buhaisi, E. (1996). *Al-Muhasaba fel Islam*.

Alexander, J. (2002). *History of Accounting*.

Budiselić, E. (2014). The Role and the Place of Tithing in the Context of Christian Giving Part 1.

Cordery, C. (2015). Accounting history and religion: a review of studies and a research agenda.

Deuteronomy 21:15-17. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Deuteronomy 21:15-17. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Deuteronomy verse 23:19. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Dhar, P. (2013). Zakah as a measure of social justice in Islamic finance: an accountant's overview.

Exodus 22:16. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Exodus verse 22:25. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Ezekiel 3:18; Ezekiel 3:20; Ezekiel 33:6; Ezekiel 33:8; Ezekiel 34:10; Daniel 6:2; Jonah 1:14 and Romans 3:19. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

(2017). *Full text of sharia'ah standards for Islamic financial institutions*. Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions ("AAOIFI").

Galatians 6:5. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Galatians 6:5. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Hossain, M. (2012). Zakah in Islam: A powerful poverty alleviating instrument for Muslim countries.

Leviticus 27:30. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Leviticus verses 25:35-37. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Luke 15:12. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Madawaki, A. (2012). Adoption of international financial reporting standards in developing countries:
The Case of Nigeria.

Napier, C. (2007). Other cultures, other accounting? Islamic accounting from past to present.

Nataliya, M. (2013). *History of origins and development of system international accounting*.

Numbers 18:28. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Numbers 27:8-11. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Numbers 4:27. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Proverbs 13:22. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Proverbs 19:14. (n.d.). In *Holly Bible*.

Surat Al-Baqarah verse 275. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Baqarah verse 276. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Baqarah verse 43. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Baqarah verse 83. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Imran verse 139. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Nesa verse 11. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Nesa verse 12,13 and 14. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Nesa verse 7. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

Surat Al-Nesa verse 77. (n.d.). In *Holly Quran*.

(2018). *Use of IFRS standards around the world*. IFRS.

Wealthigorilla. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://wealthigorilla.com/most-influential-people/>

(2016). *Zakah accounting standard*. Saudi Organization for Certified Public Accountants "SOCPA".